

AUTOMATION SYSTEMS OF PRODUCTION PROCESSES

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Abstract. *In this article, we will talk about automation systems of production processes and their importance in the development of society.*

Key words: *systems, processes, production, automation, level, mechanism.*

СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЗАЦИИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ

Аннотация. *В этой статье мы поговорим о системах автоматизации производственных процессов и их значении в развитии общества.*

Ключевые слова: *системы, процессы, производство, автоматизация, уровень, механизм.*

INTRODUCTION

Production automation — mechanized entrusting control and management work to automatic devices; high level of mechanization. One of the main directions of science and technology development: labor productivity, product quality, work culture, factors allows to raise its indicators to a higher level. There are partial (local), gross (complex) and full automation stages. In the stage of partial automation, adjustment of individual work types (liquid level height, temperature, pressure, etc.) is automated. At the stage of gross automation, several partially automated work types are interconnected at the department, workshop, enterprise scale.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION

Some automation tools have been around for a long time. However, such devices were practically not used in small-scale craft fairs (until the 18th century). As a result of the improvement of labor tools and equipment, the creation of new machines and mechanisms (19th century) its size and level have changed dramatically.

This situation created the necessary conditions for the mechanization of production (for example, in spinning, weaving, metal and wood processing enterprises). Since the invention of the voltage regulator at the beginning of the 20th century, electricity from it used in; multi-operation aggregate-machines and automatic lines are created. Automation concept appeared during this period.

Automated control devices and mastering processes began simultaneously with the establishment of heavy industry and machine-building (in the 1930s). Automated devices began to be used in heavy, light and food industries, and transport automation became more sophisticated. Automation labs were established in energy, metallurgy, chemistry, mechanical engineering, utilities, scientific research institutes. 50's By the 1960s, automation was used in almost all branches of the national economy.

Full automatic control of hydroelectric power units was switched over, water supply systems and fields were automated. [3.21] The scientific basis of production automation has developed mainly in three directions. First, effective methods of studying the laws, dynamics, stability and influence of external factors of management objects were developed. Researchers, designers,

technologists solve these issues together. Secondly, the effectiveness of management methods, the purpose of the management function was determined. Based on this, the decision-making rules for management were defined. Thirdly, thorough, simple and effective engineering methods of harmonizing the structure of automation tools that perform measurement, result processing and control functions have been developed.

But work on improvement and development of production automation continues continuously. In workshops, warehouses and other places of production, the compilation and preliminary processing of information (information) is carried out by means of keyboard devices, the collected information is transferred to processing. [4.109]

Sensors are used for automatic recording of information. Information transmission equipment consists of signal converters, telemechanics equipment, signal distribution switches and a section. Logical and mathematical information processing devices - functional converters that change the character and form of signals, include devices (including computers) that process information according to a given algorithm and it.

It includes information display devices (including computers) and the like. Information display devices - signal boards, mnemonic schemes, spindle and digital tools, electron-beam tube, letter and digital printing machines show the progress of production processes to the operator and record important parameters. [3.62]

Devices that produce control effects convert weak information signals into strong pulses. These impulses act on the actuators of protection, adjustment or control devices and activate them. A set of information gathering and preliminary processing tools allows to automate the management of national economic networks. [1.89]

In the automation of the management of production processes, control and adjustment circuits, analytical techniques and software control systems that allow production to be carried out in an optimal (optimal) mode are also very important. For example, in hydroelectric plants, the water from the reservoir continuously passes through the turbines of the hydro aggregate.

Automatic adjusters adjust the number of revolutions of the turbines, the frequency and voltage of the generated current, active (active) and reactive powers. Safety devices prevent accidents. The auto operator starts and stops the units according to the schedule. The dispatcher of the energy system controls the HPP remotely (from the central control panel) using a telemechanic devices. Almost all hydroelectric power stations in Uzbekistan work in this order.

Thermal power plants are more difficult to manage. The "boiler-turbine-generator-transformer" block with a capacity of several hundred MW consists of various aggregates. For example, an 800 MW unit has about 1,000 control objects and about 1,300 controlled parameters. One engineer-operator manages these objects and parameters with the help of an automatic control system.

Chemical, petrochemical, gas and pharmaceutical industries with continuous technological processes, water supply, sewage, etc. can also be automated. Along with the improvement of rock crushing methods in mining, thermal, electric and acoustic crushing methods are being developed, which allow for effective automation of this work; EHM (electronic calculator) and computers are used in mines. [3.104]

Mineral processing processes in metallurgy are mainly carried out cyclically. During blast furnace production, all key parameters are automatically measured and adjusted. EHM and

computers are used in the heating control system. Gas consumption in Marten ovens is automatically adjusted.

In rolling mills, the main operation, operation of clamping devices and control of auxiliary mechanisms are automated. With the help of computing machines, a system of cutting materials without releasing them to waste is being used. I.ch.a is the basis of technical progress in modern engineering. Along with automatic machines, multi-operation units, hydraulic, pneumatic, electric or mixed control systems have been created and are being improved.

The universality of the machines is preserved even when the work cycle of the program-controlled metalworking machines is fully automated. Automation of assembly processes is one of the complex and urgent issues of mechanical engineering. It has great economic benefits. The quality of assembled parts and components is automatically checked continuously during assembly.

Nowadays, machine-building enterprises work at a rapid pace and that the produced products can compete in the world market in order to ensure the effectiveness of technological methods, equipment increasing their reliability and accuracy and on a large scale automation is important. Improvement and creation of innovative ideas and technologies is one of the main tasks of today. Nowadays, science and technology, rather, it is difficult to imagine the development of the entire society without automation, because it is difficult to find any field where automated technologies are not used difficult. [2.81]

Production industry activities of developed countries and in them control and management of technological processes of modern scientific and technical development based on its characteristics.

The concept of development of High productivity in all sectors of industry modern in creating reliable, cost-effective technological equipment: One of the urgent problems is to ensure the widespread use of technologies is considered one. In this regard, developed foreign countries, that is USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea, China, Russia and others. Certain achievements have been achieved in the countries, and production in them increase efficiency, ensure product quality and competitiveness for management of technological processes in machine-building enterprises and special attention is paid to automation.

Production of science and technology has continuously developed in recent years frequent changes in the type of products in enterprises, production facilities changing and shortening the period of mastering new types of products is coming This, in turn, is an automated technological and assistant methods of designing and calculating equipment and their control systems requires development.

CONCLUSION

The degree of automation of mechanical engineering today focused on the creation of automated machine systems various stages of production - from preparation of it to collection includes currents. In this case, the automation center is fully developed based on the transition from production to serial production. This is it in turn, automation of auxiliary technological processes and mechanization and economic, organizational and management system issues related to finding a solution.

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